

THE ESSENCE OF THE INTERNATIONAL INVESTMENT FORUM AND THE IMPORTANCE OF ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS

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The international investment forum is a convenient space created to discuss the implementation of strategic initiatives and to demonstrate the country's investment opportunities to the international business community.

In fact, as a result of geopolitical tensions between foreign countries, disruptions in the supply chains of goods and services, a decrease in international trade, a decrease in investment flows, and an increase in climate disasters occur. The growth rate of the world economy has been declining in recent years. According to the International Monetary Fund, it will decrease by 3.5% in 2022 and 2.9% in 2023. Trends in foreign direct investment are also falling short of forecasts. According to UNCTAD, in 2022, the flow of foreign direct investment decreased by 12%, and in 2023, it increased by 3%. In 2023, the total volume of investments in developing countries decreased by 9 percent. Of course, there is a struggle between countries in order to attract investment resources in the world. The principle of mutual trust and mutual support between the countries remains a strong pillar of long-term cooperation.

In order to introduce the investment potential of our country to the international business community, to attract foreign investors, including international financial institutions, large companies and corporations, who are interested in achieving the priority goals of economic development and expanding their activities in the economy of our country, "Tashkent International Investment forum" is held every year. Because this major event plays an important role in demonstrating Uzbekistan's investment opportunities to the world community.

It is known that in the conditions of economic fluctuations in the world financial and commodity markets, a stable and reliable financial environment and entering the market and operating in it are important for international business representatives. By bringing together large investors, foreign and local business representatives, this international event created a favorable environment for them to find common interests, study specific investment projects, discuss the latest trends in dozens of areas, and accept promising proposals. In turn, it demonstrates the potential of Uzbekistan, which is showing stable growth rates, has a favorable investment environment for foreign

investors, and is gradually becoming a real investment center of Central Asia. Through this, investors were given the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the conditions and benefits created in our country and thereby attract foreign investments to promising projects.

In fact, in recent years, an international investment forum has traditionally been held at the initiative of the head of our state. When this forum was held for the first time in 2022, it was received with great interest by many foreign government leaders, the world's leading international financial institutions, large companies, business representatives, and investors.

Over the past three years, this forum has become an effective forum for expanding bilateral and multilateral cooperation, discussing the most pressing issues, and developing advanced ideas and approaches. On April 29, our President got acquainted with the presentation on preparation for the Third Tashkent International Investment Forum. It is known that the influence and scope of this conference is growing. More than 1,000 foreign guests from 56 countries attended the first forum held in 2022, and this year more than 2,500 people from 93 countries participated in the event.

In 2022, 105 documents worth 7.8 billion dollars were signed at the investment forum, and in 2023, the total amount of contracts was 11 billion dollars and 3.2 billion dollar more or increased by 40 percent than the previous year. Within the framework of the forum, the investment potential of the regions of Uzbekistan and more than 160 large projects were presented to foreign partners, and agreements were reached on the implementation of investment projects aimed at stimulating the production of high-value-added products in the directions from green energy to innovative industry, from agriculture to digitization of economic sectors.

A portfolio of contracts and deals worth 17 billion dollars has been formed for the Tashkent International Investment Forum to be held this year. Events related to the launch of large projects, important for our economy, were also held.

Our economy has almost doubled in recent years. By the end of last year, this growth was 6 percent. Inflation has been reduced to 9 percent. Trade turnover indicators are constantly increasing. The stability of gold-currency reserves is maintained.

In recent years, more than 60 billion dollars of foreign investments have been absorbed in our country. More than 14 billion dollars of funds from

international financial institutions were attracted to the social and infrastructure sectors.

The volume of foreign investments almost doubled last year. At the same time, in the field of energy, "ACWA Power", "Masdar", "Total Eren", "Voltaia", "Çalık" and "Aksa"; "Air Products", "Indorama" and "Kamse" in chemical industry, "Orano" and "DANIELI" in mining and metallurgy, "BYD", "Kia" and "Samsung" in automotive and electrical engineering, "Koç" in construction and more than 300 investment and industrial projects have been launched and hundreds of thousands of new jobs have been created.

Also, establishing a modern energy system, reforming the banking and financial system, financially supporting promising projects in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship, increasing energy efficiency in industry and trade, transport system, industrial enterprises, improving water supply and urban infrastructure, tourism Mutually beneficial projects such as development of infrastructure, production and service sectors, development of natural resources and development of light industry network were discussed.

The International Investment Forum serves to bring the cooperation with international financial institutions and foreign investors to a new level by introducing the high possibilities of industrialization in the national economy and its investment potential to the international business community.

The event was attended by government representatives, heads of large companies, high-ranking guests from organizations such as the UN, the International Monetary Fund, OPEC, and the SCO. The increasing number of participants indicates the interest of foreign countries in establishing and strengthening mutually beneficial cooperation with our country.

The forum is a convenient place to demonstrate the economic potential of our country and agree on mutually beneficial projects. Therefore, there are many events and issues to be discussed within its framework. In particular, more than 40 events, including sections, roundtable discussions and presentations, were held, including branch meetings, roundtable discussions, presentations, intergovernmental commission meetings. The launch ceremony of a number of projects in our country is also planned.

The forum provides a unique opportunity to establish business relations in promising sectors such as digital transformation, development of transport and logistics routes, infrastructure and green economy. The most important part of the forum was the launch ceremony of a number of large projects with the participation of foreign partners. Within the forum contracts were signed with

the leading companies of the world, "Linde", "Orascom", "DataVolt", "Bonafarm", "PASHA holding" and other companies on the implementation of large projects in our country.

It is planned to widely implement the experience of implementing public-private partnership projects in the field of energy in social and other infrastructure sectors. In particular, the projects of irrigation and highways with the Chinese companies "Sitik" and "Kamse", drinking water supply with the French companies "Suez" and "Veolia", and the construction of modern medical facilities with the Arab companies "Inter Health" and "Pure Health" are being developed.

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